

Doing AI Differently

Methodology report

Innovations in intentional
field formation and upstream
humanities integration

The
Alan Turing
Institute

The Doing AI Differently initiative demonstrates how research communities can be systematically cultivated around complex challenges that exceed current disciplinary boundaries. Over 18 months, this approach engaged 150+ researchers across 40+ institutions and 6 continents, achieving adoption as a £1M programme theme at UK Research & Innovation with international co-funding.

The methodology presents two key innovations: **upstream humanities integration** (incorporating interpretive expertise early in technology development) and **intentional field formation** (creating collaborative spaces for interdisciplinary inquiry). These approaches offer direct applications to national and international AI strategies, including the UK's AI Opportunities Action Plan, whilst providing transferable frameworks for accelerating innovation across domains from sustainability to healthcare.

This report documents the systematic processes underlying the Doing AI Differently white paper, providing practical tools for replication and evidence-based validation.

1 Methodological foundations

The methodology combines three interconnected approaches enabling generative collaboration across epistemic boundaries:

1.1 Problem space articulation

The research identified and characterised problem spaces – dynamic landscapes of questions, resources, paths, and relationships that transcend disciplinary boundaries, building on problem space theory¹ and Open Prototyping frameworks.²

This combined early conceptual visioning by the core team with participatory facilitation and emergent discovery, engaging scholars across disciplines to shape foundational themes and mobilise aligned contributors.

Open Prototyping, developed since 2015 by the initiative's leadership, is a framework for collaborative inquiry that bridges epistemic cultures while holding space for difference. It enables structured engagement across disciplines, maintaining contradictions as resources for innovation, and includes public-facing activity to stimulate field formation.

1 Lury, C. (2021). *Problem Spaces: How and Why Methodology Matters*. Polity Press. ISBN 9781509507948

2 Hemment, D. (2020). *Reordering the Assemblages of the Digital through Art and Open Prototyping*. *Leonardo*, 53(4). MIT Press. DOI: 10.1162/leon_a_01861

Key tools and methods include:

Problem space & design space canvas: Structured discussion and visioning of context, current landscape, critical gaps, convergent direction, and novel concepts.

Four-dimensional exploration: Systematic investigation across Aspect (data, ethics), Algorithm (technology, architecture), Affect (people, experience), and Apprehension (learning, meaning).

Diffraction analysis: Dynamic exploration of the tensions and interferences that are generative between concepts, disciplines, practices, and perspectives.³

These were deployed using a combination of printed canvases and digital platforms such as Mural and Slido, enabling hybrid collaboration across in-person and distributed formats.

Sidebar

This methodology builds on prior work in AI arts and design research, notably The New Real and experiential AI, which helped shape the collaborative and interpretive orientation of the approach.

Sidebar

A factor in the initiative's success is it was catalysed by an invitation from the AI engineering community (Adam Sobey, The Alan Turing Institute) to reshape the foundations of AI engineering through the humanities.

³ Concept adapted from Barad, K. (2007). *Meeting the Universe Halfway: Quantum Physics and the Entanglement of Matter and Meaning*. Duke University Press. ISBN: 978-0-8223-3917-5

1.2 Community mobilisation

Sustainable interdisciplinary collaboration requires deliberate structuring of relationships and shared inquiry, serving both as a foundation and as a generative engine for methodological development. The community coalesced through a combination of purposeful scaffolding and facilitated emergence, designed to empower rather than extract.

Iterative workshop series: Custom-designed structured but adaptable formats that build from exploratory inquiry to concrete programme development.

Contributory authorship: Novel collaborative writing processes enabling large-scale input (50+ contributors) while maintaining coherence through structured seed-draft development, targeted contributions, and iterative synthesis.

Multi-modal engagement: Community calls, targeted outreach, public events (e.g. AI UK), blogs, and multiple entry points addressing power dynamics that exclude diverse voices.

1.3 Epistemic translation

Enabling generative dialogue across disciplinary boundaries whilst protecting against knowledge appropriation is a core methodological process within the initiative.

Boundary-spanning roles: Individuals operating across epistemic cultures as mediators without losing disciplinary credibility, essential for navigating fundamental differences in approaches to evidence and validity.

Structured dialogue: Open Prototyping frameworks enabling constructive exchange without erasing relational dimensions or disciplinary differences.

Equity-oriented practices: Tangible efforts to address equity and reduce extractive dynamics whilst remaining sensitive to tokenistic representation.

Sidebar

The initiative was aided by early recruitment and engagement of individuals who could model new ways of thinking while enabling others to contribute.

2 Implementation process and community engagement

2.1 Four-phase development

Phase 1: Scoping and visioning: Identified a latent interdisciplinary opportunity space (human-AI synergies), three interconnected challenges (the qualitative turn in AI, the homogenisation problem, transformations in human cognition), and three corresponding themes (interpretive technologies, alternative architectures, human-AI ensembles) through conceptual visioning work and extensive cross-disciplinary outreach.

Phase 2: Community convening: Sustained engagement across multiple channels and three structured international workshops:

- Pittsburgh (October 2024): Concept validation and methodology testing
- Edinburgh (February 2025): Problem space articulation with design canvases
- London (March 2025): International validation with 70+ experts from 40+ institutions

Phase 3: Collaborative knowledge production: Contributory authorship achieving 50+ scholar input whilst maintaining intellectual coherence, with iterative refinement through workshops and expert review. Also working groups supported early-stage concept development.

Phase 4: Strategic alignment and validation: UK Research & Innovation (UKRI) programme theme adoption with international co-funding; broadbased engagement of intergovernmental organisations and industry; UK government policy engagement (UK Department for Science, Innovation and Technology, GO Science)

August 2023	•	Theme lead appointed
October 2023	•	Initial theme vision
December 2023	•	Engagement at UK and US institutions
January 2024	•	UK Research & Innovation engagement
March 2024	•	AIUK events & workshops
May 2025	•	AHRC seed funding
June 2025	•	Invited expressions of interest
July 2025	•	Turing university network & industry engagement
October 2024	•	Research associate appointed
October 2024	•	Pittsburgh workshop
December 2024	•	ISPF sandpit & funding call confirmed
January 2025	•	White paper seed draft circulated
February-March 2025	•	Contributory authorship
February-March 2025	•	Working groups convened
February-July 2025	•	Technical reviews & policy engagement
February 2025	•	Edinburgh workshop
March 2025	•	First full draft of white paper
March 2025	•	London workshop
March-ongoing 2025	•	Various research collaborations
August 2025	•	White paper published
August 2025	•	ISPF sandpit & funding call launched

2.2 Participation ethics and power balance

While international in participation, the initiative is currently concentrated in Anglophone institutions. However, tangible efforts were made to increase inclusion and reduce extractive dynamics. These included:

- Structured processes ensuring equitable participation across disciplinary hierarchies.
- Explicit recognition of humanities expertise as essential rather than supplemental.
- Striving for gender balance in participants and contributors.
- Inviting contributors from Indigenous communities as participants and co-authors.
- Paying fees to unaffiliated contributors such as independent artists, recognising financial precarity and sectoral inequities.

3 Evidence and impact validation

3.1 Quantitative metrics

Community formation: 150+ researchers, 40+ institutions, 6 continents.

Institutional adoption: Programme theme adoption at UKRI with international co-funding (£1M).

Knowledge production: 50+ contributing authors, multiple publications in development, policy note with recommendations.

3.2 Qualitative validation

Engagement spanning academia, industry, government, and civil society demonstrates capacity to bridge sectoral as well as disciplinary boundaries. High levels of active collaboration among the emerging community demonstrates potential for lasting rather than temporary collaboration. Discovery of complementary international efforts confirms methodology's ability to recognise authentic inflection points for interdisciplinary collaboration. Rapid institutional response within established funding frameworks validates identified research needs.

4. Transferability and applications

4.1 Replicable framework

Core requirements for successful replication:

- Boundary-spanning visioning and facilitation with domain expertise and cross-cultural translation capabilities.
- Institutional convening power enabling multi-stakeholder engagement.
- Funding flexibility supporting iterative development.

Transferable tools include problem space canvases, workshop templates, contributory authorship processes, and validation methods.

4.2 Institutional innovation and policy applications

The methodology provides evidence for new research organisation forms: interdisciplinary centres designed around problem spaces rather than disciplines, policy-research integration mechanisms, and industry-academia partnerships structured for genuine knowledge co-production.

For policy makers: Upstream humanities integration provides transferable approaches for national AI strategies, with proven methods for cross-sector collaboration and international research partnerships.

For research leaders: Intentional field formation can reduce innovation timelines from decades to years through purposeful rather than organic field formation, with validated frameworks for global collaboration.

4.4 Domain applications

Incubated as part of the Turing's Sustainability Mission with wider relevance and transferability to fundamental research, healthcare, engineering design, digital governance, and other challenges requiring integration of technical and humanistic expertise.

5. Limitations & future development

5.1 Current limitations

Concentration in Anglophone institutions and need for broader Global South participation and wider engagement of impacted communities. It also benefits from structural advantages – including institutional access, funding, and intellectual capital – that are not universally available. Additionally, the initiative remains in early stages, with long-term outcomes and field-level impact yet to be demonstrated.

5.2 Platform scaling

Field-building infrastructure supporting distributed collaboration, expanded global participation, and long-term sustainability frameworks.

Conclusion

The Doing AI Differently methodology demonstrates that research communities can be systematically cultivated through structured yet emergent processes around urgent societal challenges requiring unprecedented interdisciplinary collaboration. By validating novel approaches to problem space articulation, community mobilisation, and epistemic translation, this work contributes methodological innovation and practical frameworks for responding to complex challenges.

The methodology's rapid institutional adoption and sustained community engagement show that systematic interdisciplinary research development can be designed for both rigour and transformation – integrating diverse expertise while enabling new configurations of knowledge, practice, and policy.

Full documentation of workshop processes and design tools is available through the Doing AI Differently initiative.

WHY? THE NEED OR OPPORTUNITY WE ADDRESS

WHAT? THE CORE INNOVATION WE ENVISION

Doing AI Differently, DESIGN SPACE

WHY? THE NEED OR OPPORTUNITY WE ADDRESS

HOW? WHAT MAKES THIS FEASIBLE?

Doing AI Differently

PROBLEM SPACE Canvas

Use this canvas to articulate a cross-disciplinary problem space and map connections across it, to help identify and build consensus on promising research directions.

CENTER: Title of Problem Space
 How can you articulate a research direction at the intersection of these perspectives?
 How can this advance beyond current approaches?

INNER CIRCLE: Convergent Direction
 What questions emerge across or between disciplinary boundaries?
 How can disciplinary perspectives be bridged?

MIDDLE CIRCLE: Critical Gaps
 What questions and methods are missing from current approaches?
 Where do disciplinary boundaries create blind spots?

MIDDLE CIRCLE: Current Landscape
 What existing work and knowledge can we build upon?
 How do different disciplines currently approach this?

OUTER CIRCLE: Broader Context
 What societal needs drive this work?
 What technical challenges must be addressed?

GAP BETWEEN DIAMOND AND CIRCLE
 The boundaries we broker
CROSS-CUTTING ELEMENTS
 Use lines or arrows to illustrate connections
 Identify the interferences and relations that are generative

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Thanks to: Cody Kommers (The Alan Turing Institute) and **Matjaz Vidmar** (University of Edinburgh)

The Doing AI Differently initiative is led by The Alan Turing Institute, University of Edinburgh and the UK's Arts & Humanities Research Council (AHRC-UKRI), in collaboration with international partners.

Publisher: The Alan Turing Institute, London, UK.

Publication Date: 31 July 2025.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.16421465](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16421465)

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Cite as: Hemment, D. (2025). Doing AI Differently: Methodology Report – Innovations in intentional field formation and upstream humanities integration. London: The Alan Turing Institute

Funded by: Arts & Humanities Research Council and Lloyd's Register Foundation.

This methodology report, the main white paper and policy note are available online: www.turing.ac.uk/news/publications/doing-ai-differently

This policy note has been prepared as part of: the Sustainability Mission at The Alan Turing Institute.

Doing AI Differently website: www.doingaidifferently.org

Cover image: Yutong Liu & Kingston School of Art / Better Images of AI / Talking to AI 2.0 / CC-BY 4.0.

Design and typography: Joshua Smythe, Studio Ampersandwich

Brand identity: Steven Scott, twofifths design

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The Alan Turing Institute is the UK's national institute for data science and artificial intelligence. The Institute is named in honour of Alan Turing, whose pioneering work in theoretical and applied mathematics, engineering and computing is considered to have laid the foundations for modern-day data science and artificial intelligence. The Institute's purpose is to make great leaps in data science and AI research to change the world for the better. Its goals are to advance world-class research and apply it to national and global challenges, build skills for the future by contributing to training people across sectors and career stages, and drive an informed public conversation by providing balanced and evidence-based views on data science and AI.